

MAGNETIC CONTROL OF MICROSTRUCTURE IN GRAPHENE EPOXY NANOCOMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Controlling the alignment and microstructure of graphene in polymer nanocomposites has the potential to improve and tune properties such as toughness, stiffness, thermal conductivity and coefficient thermal expansion (CTE). Drawing of fibres and films has demonstrated potential benefits but these are limited in scale and geometry. Approaches to bulk control have included freeze casting, self-assembly and applied external fields (electrical and magnetic). Magnetic fields are attractive due to the potential for bulk control of microstructure, however, previous attempts have required very high magnetic field strengths (15-25T) due to graphene's diamagnetism. Here we explore the deposition of superparamagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles on plasma functionalised graphene in order to increase magnetic susceptibility and allow particle actuation in low magnetic fields (<100mT). Microscopy techniques such as, Optical Microscopy and SEM have been used to study the alignment process and the resulting microstructures in epoxy composites. Interconnected networks of graphene have been observed at filler loadings below 1 wt. %. Quantitative study of the orientation of the magnetically controlled microstructure was determined by small-angle X-ray scattering (SAXS). By the SAXS results, the anisotropic behaviour of the magnetic graphene sheets has been confirmed in the direction of the applied magnetic field. The influence of the aligned graphene sheets was evaluated on the final thermal properties of the epoxy composites via thermal conductivity measurements. An increase of >45 % with filler loading of 2 wt. % aligned in a 100 mT field compared with a composite containing 2 wt. % of randomly dispersed fillers was observed, indicating the potential for thermal management applications.

1 INTRODUCTION

Graphene-derivatives are promising materials for use as nanofillers in polymer composites due to a unique combination of properties, such as high physical aspect ratio, high specific strength, high electronic conductivity, extraordinary thermal conductivity, and superior mechanical properties [1]. In the past few years, graphene sheets have been introduced into a wide range of polymer matrices, including epoxy, polystyrene, poly(methyl methacrylate), for various functional materials. Among them, epoxy resin, one of the most important class of thermosetting polymers, is used widely in many applications. However, the improvements achieved so far using such carbon-based nanofillers are still much lower than theoretical predictions, due to a variety of factors, including the degree of the dispersion and exfoliation [2], the interfacial interactions between the filler and the matrix [3] and the

filler orientation [4]. For mechanical reinforcement, lower volume fractions with high levels of dispersion are desirable. Whereas for thermal or electrical conductivity percolated networks, higher filler loadings are usually required and some agglomeration can be beneficial. This makes the achievement of nanocomposites with enhanced mechanical and functional properties challenging.

Different approaches have been reported in order to control the structural architecture of the nanocomposites in order to provide a better balance of improved properties. For instance, researchers have focused on the creation of porous architectures via wet-processing approaches, such as freeze-casting process [5] or emulsion-based techniques [6], creating multi-layered materials that could exhibit very interesting mechanical and electrical properties. However, these approaches are not readily scalable and lack control of their chemistry or the ability to select a desired structure for specific applications. The use of externally applied fields is an alternative approach where electrical [6] or magnetic fields [7] are utilized to align and structure nanomaterials. The scalability of these approaches can also be limited, particularly as the low magnetic susceptibility of nanocarbons means that very high magnetic fields have been required (15-25T) [8]. Thus, integrating graphene sheets with magnetic nanoparticles to form strong magnetic nanohybrids was successfully achieved and applied in epoxy composites, achieving anisotropic thermal conductivity measurements [9]. At present, the study of the mechanisms of reinforcement in polymer composites by aligned graphene sheets is still limited [10] and more investigation is needed.

In this work, we present an approach for the decoration of graphene flakes with magnetite (Fe_3O_4) nanoparticles which significantly enhances their magnetic susceptibility and allows manipulation in very low magnetic fields (<100mT). An efficient alignment of the graphene flakes was characterized through optical microscopy, SEM and small angle X-ray scattering (SAXS). We study the limit of magnetic actuation and the variation in achievable microstructures.

2 MATERIALS

Graphene nanoplatelets (GNPs) used in the present work have been plasma treated by Haydale Ltd (HDPlas@GNPs). The surface area of the GNPs was measured to $\sim 20 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$ and also, their planar size was in the range of 0.3-5 μm with thickness <50 nm. The GNPs were plasma processed in a COOH atmosphere, functionalizing them with carboxylic chemical groups (GNPs-COOH). For the deposition of iron oxide particles, the following materials were used: Iron (II) sulfate heptahydrate ($\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$), anhydrous iron chloride (FeCl_3) and ammonium hydroxide (NH_4OH , 28.0-30.0 % NH_3 basis) were sourced from Sigma – Aldrich, UK. For the magnetic measurements, Iron (II, III) oxide nanopowder (50-100 nm particle size (SEM), 97 % trace metals basis) and Iron (III) oxide nanopowder (<50 nm particle size (BET)) were provided from Sigma-Aldrich, UK. IN2 epoxy infusion resin (bisphenol-A based, with $\text{MW} < 700$) was provided by the EasyComposites Ltd. The epoxy resin was catalysed using a fast hardener (AT30), provided by EasyComposites, which has a pot-life of 9-14mins, a gelation time of 2-4hrs and is de-mouldable in around 6 hrs.

3 SAMPLE PREPARATION

GNPs are coated with magnetite nanoparticles ($\sim 30\text{nm}$ diameter) using a wet chemistry co-precipitation method [11]. X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS), TEM and diffraction were used to confirm the magnetite structure and particle size.

Epoxy nanocomposites were manufactured by dispersing the fillers (plasma treated GNPs, GNPs-COOH and iron oxide-coated GNPs, GNPs@MNP's) using dual asymmetric centrifugal mixing (Speed mixer DAC 800.1 FVZ) for 10 mins at 1950 rpm. Once complete the mixture was degassed under vacuum for 30min to remove entrained air. Following dispersion of the filler, the hardener was added at manufacturer recommended ratio (100:30 by weight) and further speed mixing (1950 rpm for 2 min) was used to combine. Mixtures were then cured for 6hrs at 25°C, followed by post curing in an oven at 60°C-12hrs.

A droplet of resin was sandwiched between two optical microscope slides using 0.2mm thick cover slips as spacers to control thickness. This allowed observation of the microstructure development under application of a magnetic field using an optical microscope (20 \times magnification, Leitz Wetzlar,

Germany, Nikon DSLR camera). The slides were then placed between the poles of a steel C-core electromagnet in parallel and perpendicular direction relating to the two poles and subject to a magnetic field (<100mT) until completion of the resin cure. The magnetic field was measured using a LakeShore 450 gaussmeter. The length distribution of resulting connected networks was measured from three optical images for each filler loading, using the ImageJ software.

The morphology of aligned graphene clusters (GNPs@MNP's) in the epoxy matrix was studied by Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) analysis using a Zeiss Sigma HD Field Emission Gun Analytical SEM. To avoid charging during electron irradiation, the samples have been sputter coated with ~20nm overlayer of Au-Pd alloy. Secondary electron images were acquired at 5 kV with an in-lens detector. Two different magnifications were used (500X and 5KX) in order to obtain a high quality image. Epoxy films containing 1 wt. % of MNPs@GNPs were prepared by cryo-fracture technique and then cut in the direction of the applied magnetic field. Figure 1 is a schematic diagram of the experimental magnetic system as well as the direction of the cutting surface of the epoxy films.

Figure 1: Experimental set-up of the magnetic system. A schematic illustration of the snapping surface of the SEM samples is presented.

2D SAXS was carried out at Xenocs -Xeuss 2.0 laboratory SAXS beamline with X-ray wavelength of 1.54 Å and a sample-to-detector distance of 2.5 M, providing the structural feature on the order of 0.5-100 nm. A Kapton cell was used as a background before the measurements. For azimuthal angle plots, scattering in 2D SAXS images at $q=0.006-0.01 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$ was integrated for every 5° in azimuthal angle. The thermal conductivities of the nanocomposites were determined by the laser flash technique using an LFA-427 Nanoflash (NETZSCH, Germany). The samples were coated with a thin layer of graphite prior to testing to increase absorption and transmission of infrared radiation energy. Three measurements were made on 10 mm x 10 mm samples, < 3 mm thick, over a temperature range of 25–95 at 10°C intervals. A laser voltage of 450 V and a pulse width of 0.8 ms were used. The thermal diffusivity of each sample was measured and converted to the thermal conductivity using the specific heat capacity estimated from that of a graphite control sample whose thermal diffusivity had been determined using the same set of conditions.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 2(a, b) shows that the horizontal application of an external magnetic field of 100 mT causes the self-assembly of the magnetic GNPs into chain-like clusters. Increasing the concentration to 2 wt. %, has the effect of forming a 2D interconnected network, aligned along the direction of the magnetic field. For the chains shown in the optical images of Figure 2, the average chain length reaches more than 100 μm for a filler loading of 1 wt. % and more than 200 μm was estimated for 2wt. %.

Figure 2: Optical Images of 1 wt. % (a) and 2 wt. % (b) aligned magnetic GNPs (GNPs@MNP's) under the applied field of 100mT, (c) length distribution of the aligned clusters.

A more detailed analysis of the microstructure using SEM revealed a distribution of the connected chains (Fig. 3) and alignment of the flakes within chains. Figure 3 (a) and (c) showed clearly the response of the magnetic graphene sheets in the parallel direction of the applied field and the interconnection among them, respectively. When the direction of the glass slide is changed perpendicularly, agglomerations of aligned clusters were observed, providing strong evidence of the anisotropic orientation of the graphene flakes.

Figure 3: SEM images of 1 wt. % aligned GNP clusters in epoxy resin. The thin film surface was orientated in parallel (a, c) and perpendicular (b, d) direction to magnetic field (100mT), H.

In order to explore quantitatively the orientation and structure of the magnetically assembled nanoparticle chains, a series of measurements has been performed on epoxy composite films reinforced by 1 wt. % random dispersed GNPs@MNP's and 1 wt. % GNPs@MNP's aligned in a 100mT magnetic field were examined using small-angle X-ray scattering (SAXS). Figure 4 confirms the anisotropic scattering and peaks in intensity corresponding to aligned flakes are at 180 degrees to each other and shift with sample rotation. The peaks are seen to shift 90° with sample rotation, confirming their correlation to the anisotropic alignment of the fillers.

Figure 4: SAXS intensities as a function of the azimuthal angle.

Initial through-plane thermal conductivity measurements were performed at 25°C on epoxy composites containing 2 wt. % of randomly dispersed and aligned GNPs@MNP's. Figure 5 shows that the epoxy resin is highly thermally insulative (0.03 W/mK) and after the introduction of randomly dispersed GNPs@MNP's the thermal conductivity is increased by 0.03% to 0.13% W/mK. The magnetic alignment of GNPs@MNP's increases further to 0.19W/mK, an improvement of 46.15% compared with the randomly dispersed material. This enhancement is associated with the interconnected network which is formed along the magnetic alignment direction as seen in the optical microscope image (Figure 2 b). This network acts as a channel for heat transport through the insulating epoxy matrix [12]. However, the improvement in thermal conductivity achieved is still low compared to previous published research [13]. There are some key factors that could negatively affect the thermal conductivity of the epoxy composites. Firstly, the speed mixing method was not sufficient to achieve uniform dispersion of the magnetic graphene sheets and possible GNPs clusters in the material cause the phenomenon of reciprocal phonon vectors which influences phonon transportation and restricts the heat flow [14]. Moreover, the planar size of the GNPs is quite small (size range: 0.3-5µm) and a recent report [15] has highlighted the importance of large lateral size (~30µm) in achieving high thermal conductivities of composites with multilayer graphene. These factors will be investigated in the future work.

Figure 5: Thermal conductivity of unmodified epoxy resin and nanocomposites at 25°C.

CONCLUSION

We have developed an approach to magnetically control graphene flakes (GNPs@MNP's) in an epoxy matrix under the application of an external magnetic field. Functionalization of the graphene nanoplatelets with Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles has enabled us the alignment of graphene fillers using very low magnetic fields (below 100mT). Optical Microscopy and SEM showed the alignment of the graphene flakes, creating a 2D interconnecting network with only 2 wt. % loading and this was quantitatively determined with small angle X-ray scattering (SAXS). Thermal conductivity measurements revealed an enhancement of more than 45% in the thermal conductivity of a 2 wt. % aligned GNPs@MNP's/epoxy composite in a parallel magnetic alignment direction. Future work will focus on the effect of dispersion using three roll milling or freeze drying as well as the effect of planar size on the thermal properties of these epoxy composites. These graphene nanohybrids (GNPs@MNP's) are promising magnetic fillers for fabrication of highly aligned graphene-based epoxy composites with controllable properties.

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